

THE COMPRESSION RESIN TRANSFER MOULDING PROCESS FOR EFFICIENT COMPOSITE MANUFACTURE

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1 Abstract

The manufacture of high performance carbon fibre composite parts can be achieved with very short cycle times by utilising compression resin transfer moulding (CRTM). This work presents one dimensional numerical calculations of the flow front and preform behaviour as a function of applied pressure to the tool. The results show that accurate prediction of the flow front may be achieved, and that the evolution of viscosity due to cure may be recreated.

2 Introduction

This work investigates the underlying principles of compression resin transfer to understand how this process can be applied to complex aeronautical profiles, such as frames and beams in the framework of EU FP7 Industrialisation of Manufacturing technologies for composite Profiles for aerospace applications (IMac Pro). By decreasing recurring costs, and reducing material wastage and finishing, this technique has been shown to provide a viable route to market for such aerospace quality composite components, see Figure 1.

Figure 1. Aerospace profiles that have been developed using variants of the compression resin transfer moulding (CRTM) process.

Aerospace composite structures are generally manufactured using prepreg autoclave techniques

that are time consuming, labour and machine intensive - limiting further growth. Resin infusion under flexible tooling (RIFT) has traditionally been utilised as a low cost alternative for the manufacture of fibre reinforced polymer composites. A major problem with this process is the relatively high void content, resulting in detriment to the mechanical properties of the composite material. Hence RTM has been pursued with high dwell pressures to eliminate effect of voids. With conventional RTM, as impregnation proceeds, the distance between the flow front and the injection gate grows. The pressure gradient and flow velocity are dramatically reduced for large parts [1]. Often this means that effects such as fibre washing may occur (due to the higher pressures required) as well as a penalty in time during the infusion process. Clearly, this is a limitation for use with fast curing systems and isothermal tools.

One appealing alternative to overcome above issues is the compression resin transfer moulding (CRTM) process. The process can be described as conventional resin transfer moulding (RTM) with the injection phase being conducted through thickness. A reduction of void content can be achieved within the composite material, and improved interfacial properties have also been reported [2]. In this process, the cavity is partially closed during the infusion phase, resulting in no pre compaction of the preform, and hence an increased initial permeability for resin to flow as the tool closes, and infusion progresses.

The CRTM process can be separated into six distinct phases (see Figure 2), where (a) the dry fibre preform is placed in the CRTM tool at temperature, (b) a measured amount of the degassed resin is metered into the open tool, (c) The tool is closed to a

predefined gap, and the cavity degassed. Simultaneously, the resin temperature increases, the viscosity drops, however, the process is fast, and therefore there is little impregnation due to capillary flow and gravity, (d) the degassing valve is shut, and the tool gap is reduced. The resin is distributed through the preform, and the preform comes into contact with the top of tool surface. The volume fraction and permeability of the preform will change due to the viscoelastic response of the preform during this compaction, (e) the preform is compressed further and the excess resin is removed from the preform until a prescribed fibre volume fraction is achieved (circa 60 %). The sample is held at a constant pressure for the remainder of the cure cycle and (f) lastly, the tool is opened, and the sample and excess resin ejected in one piece.

Figure 2. Shows a schematic of the compression resin transfer moulding (CRTM) process for steps (a) to (f) where a repeatable process is shown from insertion of preform through till a cured part.

The apparent interlaminar shear strength has been reported conducted for quasi-isotropic carbon-fibre epoxy laminates, shown in Figure 3 [3], and showed that a steady increase in the short beam shear strength was measured up to 20 Bar. The resin properties are known to remain unchanged within this range of pressures [4], and this was verified in

[3]. Based on the work of Goodwin et al. [5], the improvements in interlaminar shear strength were found to be greater than purely due to a reduction in void content.

Figure 3. Short beam shear strength versus compression resin transfer moulding (CRTM) pressure [3].

3 Literature

By the nature of the process, the parts produced in RTM are usually thin, hence the modelling can be simplified to a 2-D model neglecting flow through the thickness. Furthermore, preform deformation can also be disregarded, and permeability dealt with as an invariant [6, 7]. However, with a process such as CRTM, the permeability should vary as a function of local preform compaction stress and time. Such modelling has been addressed by Advani et al. [8] who have initially assumed that the resin flow does not interact with the preform by means of compaction, but that the preform is only compacted by direct mould contact, and later added complexity [9], where they took into account preform deformation due to pressure gradients in the fluid, leading to a coupling between the flow and the preform compaction. Chang [10] addressed a comparable situation with the preform being compressed due to viscous forces in the resin at the beginning of the compression stage. Therefore, the preform does not undergo further compaction during the process. Few papers have also dealt with a three-dimensional through thickness flow during the injection- or the compression stage: Simacek et al. [11] developed a code to model the flow in the processing of an automotive part, where they assumed that the preform remains rigid as long as it

is not in direct contact with both mould faces. A similar approach was presented by Shoejaei [12], where multiple filling modes were incorporated. Further models based on flow in deformable porous media have been used to describe through thickness flow behaviour. Ouahbi et al. [13], Park and Saouab [14] and Celle et al. [15] have developed resin film infusion models, while Michaud et al. have presented works [16, 17] on resin infusion in deformable porous media including dual-scale flow phenomena. A similar approach has been given by Preziosi et al. [18] based on the theory of mixtures. In all of these models, preform deformation due to viscous forces in the liquid was incorporated, whereas the flow was considered to be one dimensional through the thickness. The exact same situation of transverse flow through deformable fibrous preform also occurs in the resin film infusion process.

Knowledge of the fabric permeability is crucial for modelling liquid composite moulding processes. In CRTM, the permeability may be expressed as a function of fibre volume fraction or vice versa. A great deal of effort has been spent on developing permeability measurement techniques by several institutes, [19]. However, the exact permeability values for given materials has been difficult to define precisely.

Recently, continuous techniques to measure fabric permeability have become popular, as they deliver permeability values for a range of fibre volume fractions in a single experiment. Buntain and Bickerton [20] and Comas-Cardona et al. [21] have developed characterisation methods based on the compression of a (partially) saturated preform, where liquid flow is induced by the compression motion of two platens. In contrary, Park et al. [22] placed layers of preform on a grid and continuously compacted while a liquid passed the preform through the thickness. Finally, Klunker et al. [23] proposed a more accurate method for through-thickness permeability determination based on the value correction obtained from flow simulation, which takes into account the coupling between the viscous forces in the liquid and the preform stress. In their setup, a stack of preform is subjected to a transverse flow, which is similar to flow in CRTM.

In reality, the preform at the location of the flow front is usually not entirely saturated immediately after the flow front has passed, but it will be saturated gradually by build-up and subsequent removal of voids, as the air-fibre interface is replaced by a resin-fibre interface. These wetting effects and capillary phenomena are often referred to as dual-scale flow. Typically, with slow infusion process, capillary phenomena dominate filling (see Figure 4), and therefore void formation is macro-scale dominant. With very fast processes, there is little holding time (steps b-d in Figure 2), and so void formation processes are dominated by effects due to preferential inter-tow filling, and subsequent impregnation of tows.

Figure 4. Schematics to show preferential fill and void formation phenomena due to impregnation speed [24].

The pressure fields in the saturated and saturating regions are different, resulting in different apparent permeability at the saturating flow front and in the fully saturated region of the preform. As the pressure field is altered, Darcy's Law is violated at the gradually saturated regions as also noted by [20, 25, 26] with an explanation of transient permeability in [27]. The gradually saturated region is usually small compared to the fully saturated regions of the filled part, hence the slug-flow assumption, where the flow front is assumed to be sharp, dividing the preform into fully saturated and unsaturated regions may be applied to enable the use Darcy's Law along with a capillary pressure prescribed to the flow front as proposed by Michaud and Mortensen [28], else

when the unsaturated region is large, a multiphase flow approach must be used [29]. Finally, according to literature, the capillary pressure drop can usually be neglected for polymeric resins as its magnitude is often very small compared to the applied pressure [26, 30].

3 Materials and Experimental

A glass fibre plain weave fabric with an aerial weight of 163g/m² (P-D Interglas Style 92105) was used as reference for the one dimensional flow experiments. For this material, transverse permeability measurements were available from [31]. Impregnation trials were conducted using a silicone oil (Bluesil RHODORSIL 47 V 5000 provided by Silitech AG) with a viscosity of 5 Pa.s to slow down the process (roughly 300 times the viscosity of Hexcel Hexflow RTM 6 infusion resin) and prevent impregnation of the fabric due to capillary forces or gravity prior to the compression stage.

Dry compaction curves were recorded using a universal testing machine. A stack of 90 layers of the fabric were compressed between two circular plates, where the distance between the plates and the force was recorded. From this, the momentary fibre volume fraction and the corresponding compaction pressure were calculated. The compaction curve was then fit to a hyperbolic tangent model which is described later. To fit the permeability data from the literature, the Kozeny-Carman equation from [9] based on [32, 33] was used and $K_0 = 1.15e-12$ was found.

Through thickness resin flow experiments were conducted using a cylindrical vessel with a matching compression platen in a universal testing machine. The machine was run in constant pressure conditions to simulate impregnation as per step (d) from Figure 2. Several experiments under different conditions have been executed. Closing forces equivalent to 2 and 5.2 bars of pressure inside the cavity were applied. As per [34], the high aspect ratio between final part thickness and outer measures ensures that the flow is purely one-dimensional.

4 Modelling

The geometry may be divided in three regions with own characteristics: the resin film on top of the preform, the saturated preform and the dry preform. The boundary between the resin film and the saturated preform is called preform top, the saturated and the dry preform are separated by the flow front, see Figure 5, and the modelling in principle follows the scheme presented in [9].

Figure 5. Schematic shows the domain of solution.

If one neglects possible pressure losses due to viscous friction at the mould walls and resin fluxes inside the gap, the fluid pressure in the resin film is identical to the pressure applied by the tool, p_{ap} .

The flow in the impregnated preform may be described by two governing equations:

- Pressure distribution
- Flow front advancement

which are dependent on the applied pressure to the resin, the fabric permeability and the resin viscosity. The pressure in the preform is directly dependent on the pressure in the liquid, whereas the flow is affected by the local state of the preform, i.e. has a bidirectional coupling.

The equation governing the pressure distribution in the saturated preform is derived from the volume-averaged Darcy Law[35] in one dimension:

$$w_y = -\frac{K_{yy}}{\eta} \cdot \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} \quad (1)$$

where w_y is the fluid velocity in the y-direction, K_{yy} is the fabric permeability in the y-direction, η is the fluid viscosity, p is the fluid pressure and y is the position inside the domain; and the mass conservation for an infinitesimal control volume that is deformable in the y-direction only, where the deformation is described by a volumetric strain rate:

$$\frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial w_y}{\partial y} \quad (2)$$

where ε is the strain of the control volume in the y-direction and t is the time. Combining both results in:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{K_{yy}}{\eta} \cdot \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} \right) = \frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial t} \quad (3)$$

Using the true strain formulation for a precise prediction of high volume fractions

$$\varepsilon = \ln \left(\frac{H}{H_0} \right) \quad (4)$$

where H is the actual height of the control volume and H_0 is the initial height before deformation; and taking fibre volume fractions to describe the change in length, the volumetric strain rate can be written as

$$\frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial t} = -\frac{1}{V_f} \cdot \frac{\partial V_f}{\partial t} \quad (5)$$

where V_f is the fibre volume fraction of the control volume. Substitution in (3) leads to:

$$\frac{1}{\eta} \cdot \frac{\partial K_{yy}}{\partial y} \cdot \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} + \frac{K_{yy}}{\eta} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial y^2} = -\frac{1}{V_f} \cdot \frac{\partial V_f}{\partial t} \quad (6)$$

Equation (6) was proposed by Ouahbi et al. [13] and Park and Saouab [14], who based their modelling on the unified flow model introduced by Davé [36] and Kempner [37].

Expanding some derivatives results in

$$\frac{1}{\eta} \cdot \frac{\partial K_{yy}}{\partial V_f} \cdot \frac{\partial V_f}{\partial \sigma_{pref}} \cdot \frac{\partial \sigma_{pref}}{\partial y} \cdot \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} + \frac{K_{yy}}{\eta} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial y^2} = -\frac{1}{V_f} \cdot \frac{\partial V_f}{\partial \sigma_{pref}} \cdot \frac{\partial \sigma_{pref}}{\partial t} \quad (7)$$

Using Terzaghi's Relation to relate the fluid pressure p and the preform compaction stress σ_{pref}

$$p_{ap} = \sigma_{pref} + p \quad (8)$$

where p_{ap} is the pressure applied by the top of the mould; and taking the derivative with respect to y (keeping in mind that the applied pressure p_{ap} is constant) yields

$$\frac{V_f}{\eta} \cdot \left(-\frac{\partial K_{yy}}{\partial V_f} \cdot \frac{\partial V_f}{\partial \sigma_{pref}} \cdot \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial y} \right)^2 + K_{yy} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial y^2} \right) = \frac{\partial V_f}{\partial \sigma_{pref}} \cdot \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} \quad (9)$$

In order to ensure a well-conditioned problem from a numerical point of view, (9) is normalised using the following substitutions

$$\hat{p} = \frac{p}{p_{ap}}, \quad \hat{y} = \frac{y}{H}, \quad \hat{K} = \frac{K_{yy}}{K_0}, \quad \hat{\sigma}_{pref} = \frac{\sigma_{pref}}{p_{ap}}, \quad \hat{t} = \frac{t}{t_c} \quad (10)$$

and

$$t_c = \frac{\eta \cdot H^2}{K_0 \cdot p_{ap}} \quad (11)$$

Where H is the target laminate thickness, K_0 is the reference permeability and t_c is the characteristic time; resulting in

$$V_f \cdot \left(-\hat{K}' \cdot \left(\frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial \hat{y}} \right)^2 + \frac{\hat{K}}{V_f'} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \hat{p}}{\partial \hat{y}^2} \right) = \frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial \hat{t}} \quad (12)$$

and

$$\frac{\partial \hat{K}}{\partial V_f} = \hat{K}', \quad \frac{\partial V_f}{\partial \hat{\sigma}_{pref}} = V_f' \quad (13)$$

Equation (12) is a partial differential equation for p , where at $\partial K_{yy}/\partial V_f$ can be obtained from the fabric permeability and $\partial V_f/\partial \sigma_{pref}$ from the preform compaction behaviour. In order to obtain the pressure field of the flow in space and time, (12) can be considered as boundary value problem. Therefore, appropriate initial- and boundary conditions must be specified. At the upper boundary, which is represented by the preform top, the normalised resin pressure is equal to one (which equals p_{ap}), hence serving as upper boundary condition. As CRTM is usually performed with large pressures, the capillary pressure drop can be neglected. Hence, at the flow front, the resin

pressure is zero, which is equal to ambient pressure. Since void formation, which is an effect of the dynamic wetting, is not an investigated in this study, the differences in saturated and saturating permeability were omitted and the saturated permeability was used for this modelling.

To specify the initial condition, it is assumed that a small amount of resin has already penetrated the preform, where the pressure is linearly distributed between one at the preform top and zero at the flow front.

In order to derive the equation governing the flow front advancement, the Darcy pore velocity

$$w_p = -\frac{K}{\eta\phi} \cdot \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} \quad (14)$$

is applied at the flow front, resulting in

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial t} = -\frac{K_{yy}(y=L)}{\eta\phi(y=L)} \cdot \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial y}\right)_{y=L} \quad (15)$$

where ϕ is the porosity of the preform at the position of the flow front. In accordance with the pressure distribution, equation (15) is normalised using the expressions in (10) and

$$\hat{L} = \frac{L}{H} \quad (16)$$

where L is the distance between the flow front and the preform top. Additionally expressing the porosity of the preform by its fibre volume fraction

$$\varphi_{dry} = 1 - V_{f\ dry} \quad (17)$$

gives

$$\frac{\partial \hat{L}}{\partial \hat{t}} = -\frac{\hat{K}(\hat{y} = \hat{L})}{1 - V_{f\ dry}} \cdot \left(\frac{\partial \hat{p}}{\partial \hat{y}}\right)_{\hat{y}=\hat{L}} \quad (18)$$

In order to accurately represent the properties of the fibrous material in the simulation, a model describing the compaction behaviour and permeability dependence, a hyperbolic tangent model introduced was implemented. A model proposed by [9] is as follows:

$$V_f(\sigma_{pref}) = V_{f_0} + (V_{f_{max}} - V_{f_0}) \cdot \tanh^n \left(\frac{\sigma_{pref}}{P_{max}} \right) \quad (19)$$

where V_{f_0} , $V_{f_{max}}$, n and P_{max} are fitting parameters that depends on the fabric.

Similarly, the derivative used in (12) can be expressed as

$$\frac{\partial V_f}{\partial \sigma_{pref}} = V_f' = \frac{(V_{f_{max}} - V_{f_0}) \cdot n}{P_{max}} \cdot \left(1 - \tanh^2 \left(\frac{\sigma_{pref}}{P_{max}} \right)\right) \cdot \tanh^{n-1} \left(\frac{\sigma_{pref}}{P_{max}} \right) \quad (20)$$

In order to ensure compatibility with the governing equations, (19) and (20) are normalised, resulting in

$$V_f = V_{f_0} + (V_{f_{max}} - V_{f_0}) \cdot \tanh^n \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{pref} \cdot P_{ap}}{P_{max}} \right) \quad (21)$$

and

$$V_f' = \frac{(V_{f_{max}} - V_{f_0}) \cdot n \cdot P_{ap}}{P_{max}} \cdot \left(1 - \tanh^2 \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{pref} \cdot P_{ap}}{P_{max}} \right)\right) \cdot \tanh^{n-1} \left(\frac{\hat{\sigma}_{pref} \cdot P_{ap}}{P_{max}} \right) \quad (22)$$

To take into account the dependence of the preform permeability on its fibre volume fraction, several models have been published as well. A model that has often been used in the literature is the Kozeny-Carman model [15, 38]

$$K_{yy}(V_f) = K_0 \cdot \frac{(1 - V_f)^3}{V_f^2} \quad (23)$$

Where the derivative can be expressed as

$$\frac{\partial K_{yy}}{\partial V_f} = K'_{yy} = K_0 \cdot \frac{-3(1 - V_f)^2 \cdot V_f - 2(1 - V_f)^3}{V_f^3} \quad (24)$$

In accordance with the previous procedure, (23) and (24) are normalised, to give

$$\hat{K} = \frac{(1 - V_f)^3}{V_f^2} \quad (25)$$

and

$$\hat{K}' = \frac{-3(1 - V_f)^2 \cdot V_f - 2(1 - V_f)^3}{V_f^3} \quad (26)$$

The dry preform ahead of the flow front affects its advancement and should therefore also be described. Works [10, 17] have shown that the pressure applied from the tooling is entirely transferred to the fabric due to viscous forces in the fluid, thus stressing the dry preform with a pressure equal to p_{ap} .

For the dry preform, governing equations similar to those suitable for the saturated preform can be written, relating fibre volume fraction to the applied stress and the fabric permeability. It has been shown that the behaviour of dry and wet preforms is not identical [39]. The saturated preform is usually softer due to lubrication of the fabric [39, 40]. Saturation of the preform at the flow front, which itself is dependent on the preform architecture and the liquid used for infusion, also has an influence on the wetting behaviour and therefore, the flow front advancement.

After the derivation of the equations in the previous section, they were discretised using finite differences. For the time integration, a fully implicit scheme was used. From this, a program code was written in order to automate the time integration, see Figure 6.

Figure 6. Schematic to explain the numerical calculation.

6 Results

In a first step, the convergence of the solutions using different time steps and numbers of nodes was investigated and 50 Nodes with a time step of $1e-5$ was used. The numerical stability of the solution was also studied and found to be extremely stable with no oscillation observed after 1000 time steps.

The position of the flow front, the preform top and the upper mould versus infusion time are shown in Figure 7(a). This graph is well suited for a rough evaluation of the preform behaviour, as it directly shows whether it has been compacted or expanded.

Figure 7(b) presents numerical results for the identical model with the implementation of viscosity model from [41] and [42] and demonstrates that incomplete impregnation may be recreated due to the evolution of viscosity and degree of cure with time due to matrix cross linking.

(a)

(b)

Figure 7. Shows the time history of the compression resin transfer moulding (CRTM) process for (a) no cure and (b) cure.

A reasonably good agreement to uniaxial flow experiments was achieved with the numerical simulations (see Figure 8). At 2 bar pressure, the tool top touches the preform due to the low compact stress on the preform; see Figure 8(a). Under high compact stress, the preform will not touch the tool top until after this relaxation as per Figure 8(b) (this is particularly important for fast cure resins).

The experiments proved that even though the preform is not in contact with the mould faces, it is being compacted by viscous forces in the fluid. Merotte et al. state that at some point, all the resin from the gap has penetrated the preform. Thus, the preform is coming in contact with both mould faces and being directly compacted by the mould it strives to advance the flow. In contrary, Michaud and Månson [17] suggested that the flow front reaches the bottom of the mould before the preform comes in contact with the top mould. Afterwards, due to the viscoelastic behaviour of the fabric, the preform relaxes either completely or partially until it comes in contact with the top mould, reaching a uniform state of stress through the thickness. In [18], the

distinction is based on the proportion between the volume of resin and preform, which is dictated by the fibre volume fraction. If the amount of resin is large compared to the volume of fabric, the preform does relax completely, otherwise, it relaxes until it touches the top mould, which is already at the final position. Based on the model developed in this study, it could be shown that both cases may occur in the Compression RTM process.

(a)

(b)

Figure 8. The experimentally measured and numerically calculated positions of the preform top mould and flow front.

7 Conclusions

In this study, a model simulating transverse flow in deformable porous media as per the CRTM process was developed. Starting from the problem definition, the pressure distribution which is based on Darcy's Law in combination with mass conservation; and the flow front advancement described by the Darcy pore velocity were implemented. The hydro-mechanical coupling between the flow and the deformable preform was taken into account by Terzaghi's Relation. Furthermore, two constitutive equations

describing the permeability and the compaction behaviour of the fibrous preform were defined.

Results show a reasonable agreement to the experimental measurements of a flow front in an idealised 1D flow case. The results also show that fast infusion of preforms is possible using this through thickness infusion process, and is a vital step in the successful implementation of fast cure resins with large composite structures.

The next steps will incorporate viscoelastic effects of the preform relaxation and implement new boundary conditions for the process when the tool and preform top come into contact. Furthermore, precise rheo-kinetics will be implemented to describe the evolution of viscosity of the resin.

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